

THERMOMAGNETIC ANALYSIS OF THE PALEOCENE AND EOCENE SEDIMENTS OF THE TALISH MOUNTAINOUS ZONE

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Abstract

For investigation of the precise paleomagnetic observation firstly magneto-mineralogical observations, in other words investigation of the ferromagnet minerals in the rock should be made. In the article thermomagnetic analysis of the Paleocene and Eocene sediments of the Talish mountainous zone was made. For the thermomagnetic analysis magnetic parameters of the Jrs-magnets are used. Magnetic and mineralogical structure of natural residual magnetization carriers is observed by the forms of the curve and the blocking of the temperature T. The results of the determination of magnetic curvature of J observations made in Talish zone shows that main carriers of the residual magnetization are magnetite and hematite.

Keywords: Thermomagnetic analysis, Jrs curves, magnetic-mineralogical components, magnetite, hematite.

Introduction: Paleocene and Eocene old rocks are widely spread in the territory of Azerbaijan – they are present in all of the main components of geologic structures. Sediments in the zone of their formation can be easily determined by lithological content, properties of layering, and formation concluded by their color.

All the mountainous areas of Talish zone are Paleogene, near the mountain and planes are Neogene and Anthropogene old rocks. Paleogene and Eocene sediments consist of volcanic and volcanic-sediment layers. Apart from the small works this area was investigated intensively in the 1930-s by the involving of the Russian scientists. Among the most influential works M. Qashqay, S.Mehtiyev and A.Bayramov, V. Morozova, V.Renqarten, S.Khalilov, Y.Kozin and etc. can be named. S. Azizbekov (Azizbekov, 1979) observed the widely spread magmatic rocks. Thus, stratigraphic schemes of the Paleogenic layers in different types were given. However, precise and abundant stratigraphic scale of this area was not made yet.

Talish zone was complicated and mobile structural area of occurring of the volcanism in the Paleocene and Eocene periods, as well as the collection of sediments, the development of this area consisted of tectono-magmatism (Ak). Talish geosyncline is divided into regional inequalities and characterization of different volcanic and tectonic activities because of the different stages of development.

From the point of tectonism, Talish megazone is located in the direction of the Small Caucasus system, which is divided by Small Caucasus and Lower Araz. It is the part of the zone, covered by Northern Iran Qaradag, in the South-West side magmatic-sedimentary connections of the volcano Savalan with the volcanic complex of Mio-Pliocene in the North-East wing of the Azerbaijan Republic.

We know that paleomagnetic observations are made in rocks with different components and source of

occurring, that's why in the area of observation straight and reverse problems are taken into account.

The investigation of the age of rocks by paleomagnetic method depends on the time of formation of initial magnetization. Thus, the presence of the age division is vital in the zones of observations by paleomagnetic methods. For studying of local and regional tectonic movement it is enough to know the movement of the magnetization. For solution of the exact geological problems, the paleomagnetic observation is inevitable.

All laboratory methods are directed to the determination of initial magnetization In^0 during the rock formation time. The resistance of In^0 to the laboratory conditions (time, temperature, changing the magnetization direction, etc.) doesn't mean the defining of it as the initial magnetization. It is the first stage of magnetization that defines the stability of In^0 for different laboratory condition changings.

Magnetic cleaning is witnessed by demagnetization of natural remanent magnetization of rocks, first by disappearing of its second component. Magnetic cleaning is possible when second component of magnet I_s less stable than the first one under then different magnetization. Magnetic cleaning is applied in these modifications: time, temperature, non-constant magnetic field, chemical reagents. Effectiveness of this or that type of magnetic cleaning is determined by experiments.

But before the magnetic cleaning it is necessary to determine magnetic susceptibility and the presence of ferromagnetic minerals in the composition in the rock.

One of the main properties during the investigation of the chemical content of the ferromagnetic mineral is the Curie temperature above which the magnetic moment is no more ordered and ferromagnet becomes paramagnet. This transition is not observed either by chemical alteration or by change in chemical structure of the elements, and this is by secondary phase change. This transition is evidenced both by heating and cooling

periods. Thus, observed Curie temperature is thermal constant and physically stable.

According to the present thermomagnetic method, remanent saturated magnetization $J_{rs}(T_0)$ and total saturated magnetization $J_s(T_0)$ curves are created and as a result Curie point and temperature of the phase transition T_σ is determined.

Depending on the composition of minerals, for determining the Curie point widely spread magnetic research – Thermomagnetic Analysis is used.

Thermomagnetic researches are conducted by the special tool called Thermomagnetometer. Samples are heated from 20C to 700C and according to the obtained result the thermomagnetic analysis curve is built, which makes possible to calculate and determine J_s and J_{rs} changings.

Method of J_s and J_{rs} dependence on temperature makes possible to heat the sample to any temperature enough heating for any temperature and sometimes even until the 700C.

In the article the results of thermomagnetic analysis made in Paleocene and Eocene old rocks in Talish zone are given. In the comparison to other methods, the advantage of thermomagnetic method is its high sensitivity that is, if there is enough mineral (-0.01%) in the rock it is possible to determine it and measure the scale of magnetization. Information obtained by the thermomagnetic analysis of Eocene old rocks allows us to give a diagnosis for the minerals present in rocks.

Geology of observed area: Paleocene and Eocene old rocks in Talish zone are investigated in 13 intersections. Generally, from these intersections 820 samples are collected. In all of these samples demagnetization and in more than 120 samples thermomagnetic analysis is made.

Paleocene and Eocene (lower, middle and upper) old rocks consist of stages. Stratigraphy of each stage is considered separately.

Paleocene old rocks are observed in the intersection of Istisuchay and Vesharyuchay. Total thickness of this intersection is 1200-1350 meters.

Foundation of the *Globigerino-vorianta Subbatina* və *G.aff.fiblosulinoidea* fauna in the samples collected by S.Azizbayov ensures about the relation of the rocks to the Paleocene epoch. According to the facies, these intersections can be divided into three groups (from bottom to top): tuffsiltstone, tuffsandstone and tuff gravelite.

The thickness of tuffsiltstones are nearly 500 meters.

Horizons of siltstone tuffs are expressed mainly in siltstone rocks, ash tuffs, seldom sandstones, argillite and marls. Tuff sandstones are grey, dark-grey, greenish-grey, hard, mostly carbonated. Siltstones are grey, dark grey, with limestone, thin layered. Argillites are classified into grey, greyish brown and brown colors. Marls are brownish grey, plate-like and hard.

Lower Eocene rocks are investigated in Istisuchay, Gendere, Goldere, Qoveri intersections. Sediments of lower Eocene from bottom to top – initially consist of leucite tuff and trachyandesite lavas and the overall thickness is 145 meters, then conglomerate-breccia of andesite-basaltic and breccia lavas containing layers come, where the thickness of andesite basalt layer is 180 meters, and the thickness of volcanic conglomerate-breccia reach 240 meters. Top part of lower Eocene is made of picrite-trachybasalt and lavas of leucite basaltic and pyroclastic rocks with the thickness of 155-170 meters. Angle of incidence of lower Eocene sediments varies 7-13° and azimuth 560-20°.

Middle Eocene is investigated in Divagac, Mistan, Diman and Rozqov intersections. According to stratigraphic sequence sediments of middle Eocene are divided into two layers: 1) Sediment-tuff layer, which is mostly observed in Misan and Divagac intersections with the total thickness of 190 meters. 2) Layer consisting of volcanic conglomerates, autoclastic trachyandesite lavas and trachyandesite basalts are in all four intersections with the overall thickness of nearly 190-200 meters. Angle of incidence of middle Eocene sediments in Divagac, Mistan 17-23°, azimuth 10-25°, in Diman, Rozqov angle of incidence 10-25°, azimuth varies 11-19°.

Pic 1: Places, where the samples were taken.

Upper Eocene, in its turn, was observed in the Nesli, Buzeir, Peshtashar, Tangeryu intersections. Stratigraphically Upper Eocene is divided into these layers: 1) flyschoid sedimentary-magmatic; 2) trachyandesite-basaltic lavas and proxylates series; 3) tuff-sandstone sedimentary; 4) subalkaline vitro-basalt and leucite vertebrates' lavas and proxylates series. The angle of inclination of upper Eocene sediments can be

said that is 10-25 degrees in all four intersections and azimuth varies between 540-18 degrees(5).

Methodics. Petro magnetic information is required to justify types of minerals and genesis, as well as determination of natural remanent magnetization with the compatibility of spreading of its spreading in the whole fault. This information is used for determination of compliance of these samples with the ancient

magnetization and the age of the magnetization itself. Petro magnetic information plays an important role in division of intersections into layers as well as in correlation. We know that the ferromagnetic fractions in the composition of rocks have their own properties. Change in petromagnetic properties shows the properties of sediment formation, their previous geologic interpretation was previously investigated: (Molostovsky vā Chramov, 1997; Evans vā Heller, 2003; Gujikov, 2013; Pavlov, 2017; Isayeva,1991; Qarayeva,1995 etc).

Thermomagnetic observation in 100 samples taken in 12 intersections of Talish zone was investigated in the deal of mutual agreement in the laboratory of “Head Geomagnetism and Petromagnetise” of L.Shmith named Insititue of Earth Physics of Science Academy of Russia. In samples both temperature cleaning and thermomagnetic analysis were held.

During the temperature cleaning the presence of initial magnetization of rocks was evidenced.

Thermomagnetic analysis studies magnetization during $M_s(T)$ temperature dependence during the heating until 700 degrees, determination of Curie point and cooling of the sample to the room temperature. Thermomagnetic analyses were held by the help of Kappomet MFK1- FA CS3 (Czech) apparatus.

In the article dependence curves of fed remanent magnetization on temperature was considered. Samples are heated from 20 to 700 degrees and with the obtained values the thermomagnetic curves are built, which help to exactly determine the changes in J_s and J_{rs} . Relative error of the determination of the J_s value is approximately 3%. The method of measuring of dependence of $J_s(T_0)$ and $J_{rs}(T_0)$ on tempreature supplies the heating on every temperature given that is even at 700 degrees. Accuracy of determination of heat value of the sample is approximately 2 degreeec Celcium.

$J_s(T)$ vā $J_{rs}(T)$ temperature dependence relies on physical action of thermomagnetic analysis that is when $J_s(T)$ vā $J_{rs}(T)$ reaches either the Curie temperature or blocking temperature ferromagnetic properties of the magnetic material is lost. In other words, in the diagnose of the magnetic materials one of the main characteristics is the Curie temperature which is the

temperature when the ferromagnet becomes paramagnet and the orderly condition of the magnetic moments is lost. This transition does not affect on neither chemical composition nor in crystal structure. This transformation is applied both during the heating and cooling. If during the heating of the samples either first phase change or formation of the mineral (magnetic and non-magnetic) occurs, then it can be observed both in non-repeating curves of new heating and in changes in the values of $J_s(T)$ and $J_{rs}(T)$ after the heating. Dependence of Curie temperature on mineral composition makes up the main part of the thermomagneitic analysis. Curves of the remanent saturation magnetization and total saturation magnetization are built. Apart from these, Curie temperature ($J_s(T)$), blocking temperature T_σ (for $J_{rs}(T)$), as well as temperatures during the phase change $J_s(T)$ and heating processes $J_{rs}(T)$ are determined. But thermomagnetic analysis of the magnetic minerals apart from the determination of the mineral composition, allows to value their resistance to temperature affects. This stability is obtained by the volume of J_{rs}/J_{rs0} ratio.

In our observation for determination of the magnetic composition of minerals blocking temperature and characteristic of the thermamgnetic curves were used. Observed thermomagnetic incidence of the curves in the samples let us mention three types of the curves.

In our observation blocking temperature and incidence of the thermomagnetic demagnetization nature were used. According to the incidence of the thermomagnetic demagnetization, curves are divided into three groups.

To the first group are included the curves with the blocking temperature of 580⁰ C. After the initial heating and cooling J_{rs} vā J_{rs0} are almost didn't change. In other words, ratio J_{ra}/J_{ra0} is equal to one, which shows that after repeat heating curves stay the same and no first phase change occurred. Form of curves at $T = 580^0$ C shows the soft-magnet minerals. These curves were found at dark green, grey tuffs, clay, margels samples taken from middle and upperEocene rocks (img 2a).

Image 2. Thermomagnetic curves: a) first group b) second group

To the second group are related samples which blocking temperature according to the J_{rs} (T) dependence on the curves are $T = 660-680^{\circ}\text{C}$. J_{rs}/J_{rs0} is equal to 0,8 – 1,0 and it shows the relative resistance of magnetic minerals to the temperature influence. For this group magnetization curves of temperature are relatively straight, which shows the increasing of more thin parts of magnetic minerals. Decrease of initial I_{rs0} values after heating and I_{rs} values after cooling shows that initial heating of samples after 100-150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ depends on viscous components. Path of J_{rs} (t) temperature dependence curves and the blocking temperature of $T\sigma \approx 680^{\circ}\text{C}$ shows that in this type of rocks the magnet carrier is hematite. The second group is included into middle and upper Eocene layers. They are present in tuff siltstone and silica lavas (img 2b).

Groups which show the sudden change in curve during the thermal magnetization at 300-400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ are present (img 2c), they are related to the third group. This behavior of curves can be explained by the iron sulfide (pyrrhotite, goetite) presence. By the stage heating of the pyrrhotite samples, at the $T\sigma = 320-380^{\circ}\text{C}$ blocking temperature the magnetization component is destroyed.

This phase disappears during the repetitive heating, which shows the instability in pyrrhotite heating. Complete destroying of J_{rs} at 580-600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ shows that $T\sigma = 580^{\circ}\text{C}$ another phase is magnetite. J_{rs}/J_{rs0} for these curves are 0,26-10,00. In several occasions, J_{rs} increase is evidenced after heating, which is explained by the magnet formation for titanomagnetite (img 2c) (4).

Comparison with the thermomagnetic and mineralogical observations of the magnetization of changing magnetic fields shows that reasons of J_n high resistance is not that difficult to explain. For an instance, in 58,64,84,341 samples there is only one ferromagnetic mineral – magnetite size 0,2-0,15 mk, in 2072,2050 samples – hematite size 0,3-0,15 mk.

Changing 400 Er amplitude magnetic field is weakly affected to the remanent magnetization. Thus,

we say that the samples containing magnetite and hematite are magnetostable. That is why we can surely say that the samples containing either magnetite or hematite are stable from the magnetic side(3).

Conclusions. It can be said that the heating of the magnetic minerals showed that during the again heating of these minerals curves stay stable. It should be mentioned that the curves are determined, when during the thermomagnetic analysis J_{rs} , $T\sigma$ is evidenced the fastest downfall and the values are equal to zero.

Thermomagnetic analysis applied on rocks determined the remanent magnetic carriers – magnetite and hematite. Presence of magnetite and hematite on the samples is verified by the Analytic Center of Institute of Geology and Geophysics of National Science Academy Republic of Azerbaijan.

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